

THE MORPHOLOGICAL TYPOLOGY OF THE ONOMATOPOETIC WORDS IN CHINESE AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Imitations as a term have a history of several thousand years in the world linguistics. Imitations, which are also included in language theories, play an important role in the linguistics of every language. The article discusses the research of onomatopoeic words in Uzbek and Chinese languages by the linguistic scientists, the role of onomatopoeic words in the grammar of both languages, and what category they belong to. In addition to the importance of word groups and their categorization in the classification of onomatopoeic words, the author highlights the views of several groups of linguists such as Uzbek linguists Usmonov, Qo'ng'urov, Abdurahmonov; Chinese linguists Ding Shengshu, Ma Zhen, and Wang Li and the differences between them. Opinions are given on the morphological category to which imitative words belong in both Chinese and Uzbek languages.

Key words: morphology, onomatopoeic words, interjection, derivation, noun, adjective, quantitative words, verb.

Introduction: Imitative words, which constitute a distinct group in terms of the linguistic nature of language and occupy a specific position within the system of parts of speech, have long been one of the most debated issues among linguists worldwide. The etymology of imitative words as a term dates back to ancient Greek linguistics, as described in detail by Liddell. The term onomatopoeia, derived from Latin and Greek, denotes "naming" and is interpreted as words formed from existing sounds in the surrounding world.

Unlike other parts of speech, imitative words did not attract scholars' attention at an early stage. Even during the initial development of linguistics, researchers did not recognize them as independent lexical units. One of the main reasons for this was the insufficient understanding of the distinction between imitation and imitative words. This also led to different interpretations of sound-imitative terminology across languages.

In Turkic linguistics, special studies devoted to imitative words began to emerge after the 1920s, and this category has been explored to varying degrees in most Turkic languages. In Uzbek linguistics, however, this issue was not studied as a separate object of research until the 1960s. Prior to that, grammars and manuals of the Uzbek language devoted very little attention to imitative words, and in most cases, they were treated as an integral part of interjections.

Imitative words are considered a historical category. Their emergence corresponds to a stage when humans acquired a relatively high level of control over their speech organs. In primitive times, descriptive words were extremely rare or almost nonexistent. In this regard, B. M. Yunusaliyev notes: "Sound-imitative words are not attested in the vocabulary of the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments".

R. Qo'ng'urov also agrees with this view.

From the second half of the 20th century, the issue of imitative words began to attract the attention of scholars. They conducted various observations and put forward their own views. For example, A. N. Kononov, in his work *Grammar of the Uzbek Language*, did not pay much attention to imitative words; he only mentioned sound-imitative words, emphasizing that they constitute a significant part of word-formation bases in Uzbek. Although no separate definition was given, they were treated as one of the three semantic types of interjections. However, in his later work *Grammar of Modern Turkish Literary Language*, he distinguished them as a separate

part of speech. Thus, although Kononov initially regarded descriptive words as a type of interjection, he later concluded that they should be classified as an independent category and firmly stated this view in his subsequent works.

Material and methods: N. I. Ashmarin firmly adhered to the view that all words in languages originated from imitative words. According to him, in the earliest stages, language consisted solely of mimemes, and only later did articulated speech sounds emerge from them. He argues that language underwent a period of selecting and accumulating speech sounds before forming initial words. The reason we cannot determine the imitative origin of many modern words, according to Ashmarin, is that we do not know which features of objects led to the formation of mimemes that later became stable lexical units. Therefore, he emphasizes the importance of studying gestures, body movements, natural sounds, and even the “languages” of animals and birds in order to understand the origin of language and compare them with modern linguistic systems.

A. G‘ulomov, in his textbooks for schools and in his work *Introduction to Uzbek Morphology*, initially classified imitative words as a type of interjection. However, in his report at the 1957 republican conference on improving the teaching of the Uzbek language, he stressed the necessity of distinguishing them as a separate category. Similarly, U. Tursunov, J. Muxtorov, S. Mutallibov, and S. Usmonov treated imitative words as an independent part of speech.

Based on his long-term experience, S. Mutallibov published an article on imitative words in 1956 in the newspaper *O‘qituvchilar gazetasi*. In this work, both sound-imitative and descriptive words were referred to under a single term. Although some inconsistencies were present, he later clarified his views in subsequent works. However, he occasionally confused sound-imitative words with words describing movement or state (e.g., *yalt-yult*, *g‘imir-g‘imir*), which should instead be classified as descriptive (image-based) words. Mutallibov defined imitative words as follows: “Words formed by conventionally imitating sounds produced by humans, animals, birds, insects, and objects are called sound-imitative words.” This definition, however, does not fully encompass all aspects of imitative words, particularly those related to states and imagery.

In *Modern Uzbek Language*, imitative words were briefly identified as a separate category under the term “mimemes.” Meanwhile, in the textbook by U. Tursunov and J. Muxtorov, imitative words were defined as reflections (copies) of sounds, movements, and states of entities in the external world.

R. Qo‘ng‘urov made a significant contribution to the study of imitative words in Uzbek linguistics. His research resulted in numerous articles and a monograph titled *Imitative Words in the Uzbek Language* (1966), where he analyzed their phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and syntactic features.

In the work *Modern Uzbek Literary Language*, published under the general editorship of G‘. Abdurahmonov and written by E. Begmatov, imitative words are presented under the term “descriptive words” (*tasviriy so‘zlar*), and relatively broader information is provided about them. In this work, descriptive words are defined as follows: “Words that arise through imitation of various sounds in the objective world, as well as the figurative states of the movement of objects and phenomena, are called descriptive words.”

However, in the book *Historical Grammar of the Uzbek Language: Phonetics, Morphology and Syntax*, later published under the editorship of the same author, imitative words are not included among the parts of speech. The scholar divides parts of speech into independent and auxiliary words. Independent words, in turn, are divided into nouns, verbs, and adverbs, while nominal words are subdivided into nouns, adjectives, numerals, and pronouns. Although auxiliary words include postpositions, conjunctions, particles, and conditionally interjections, imitative words are not listed among them.

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Another Uzbek linguist, Shavkat Rahmatullayev, also includes imitative words in grammar under the name “descriptive units.” The scholar defines a descriptive unit as the symbolic expression, formed by means of linguistic units, of various surrounding sounds, movements, and states. He emphasizes that there is a difference between imitation and a descriptive word. If a person reproduces the sound made by an animal, that person is imitating the animal; however, the sound uttered by the person does not itself constitute imitation. Rather, a symbolic expression of the animal’s sound is produced through linguistic means. It is precisely through this distinction that Sh. Rahmatullayev attempts to explain the difference between imitation and descriptive words.

In Uzbek linguistics, R. Qo‘ng‘urov made a significant contribution to the study of descriptive, or imitative, words.

As a result of R. Qo‘ng‘urov’s scholarly observations on descriptive words, a number of articles emerged, including “Some Reflections on Imitative Words in the Uzbek Language,” “On the Phonetic Features of Descriptive Words in the Uzbek Literary Language,” “On the Study of Imitative Words in Uzbek,” “On the Lexical Features of Descriptive Words,” and “The Semantic Classification of Descriptive Words in Modern Uzbek.” He generalized the overall description of descriptive words in Uzbek linguistics, their structure, their place in the word-formation system, and their phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and syntactic features. In 1962, he defended his candidate dissertation on this subject, and in 1966 his monograph *Descriptive Words in the Uzbek Language* was published. At the end of this work, a concise dictionary of descriptive words is also provided.

In the section of the monograph entitled “From the History of the Study of Descriptive Words,” R. Qo‘ng‘urov discusses the study of descriptive words in Turkology and comments, to varying degrees, on the views of Turkological scholars regarding descriptive words.

In 1978–1980, R. Qo‘ng‘urov’s work *Invariable Words in Modern Uzbek* was published. The second part of this work is devoted to the study of imitative and modal words. The author’s earlier views on this subject were supplemented with new insights, and the material was presented in a form suitable for the educational process.

In particular, the work contains sections on the phonetic formation of imitative words, their semantic types, structure, role in word formation, and functions in the sentence. At the same time, a section entitled “The Stylistic Features of Descriptive Words” was included.

According to the author of the work, descriptive words are used to add precision and vividness to the content expressed in a sentence. They have no other function. They do not introduce any other change into the meaning of the sentence. For this reason, if a descriptive word is omitted from a sentence, no major change occurs in its meaning; only its descriptive quality is lost. This fact, above all, shows that descriptive words are a stylistic category. These views of the author are similar to the views of Wang Li cited above, and we can observe that linguists regard imitative words not as a grammatical phenomenon, but rather as a stylistic phenomenon.

Result and discussions: Imitative words are actively used in oral speech, literary works, and folklore, giving speech artistic coloring and expressiveness. At the same time, they are also important in reflecting objective reality in general, performing a communicative function, and serving as constructional material in language.

Certain similarities and differences can be observed between the views and opinions of Chinese scholars and Uzbek scholars regarding imitative words. In order to demonstrate this, let us examine the opinions of several linguists.

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Although in China the study of imitative words began somewhat later than the study of other parts of speech or grammatical units, it has passed through a century-long evolutionary process. As scholars sought to reveal the characteristics of imitative words, the first problem before them became the search for a term in Chinese that would express their features. Different linguists have given different names to words expressing imitation. In particular, Ma Zhen (马真), in his work on grammar, states that words imitating various sounds are called “拟声词” or “象声词”; however, he himself prefers the term “象声词” and subsequently uses this term to refer to imitative words. Another Chinese scholar, Ding Shengshu (丁声树), did not dwell separately on imitative words or provide a definition for them. Nevertheless, he recognized imitative words as the final, tenth part of speech in Chinese morphology under the name “象声词.” Zhu Dexi (朱德熙), one of the prominent scholars who provided a general account of theoretical Chinese grammar, likewise did not give a separate definition of imitative words, but listed them as “拟声词” within the category of separate parts of speech.

A somewhat different approach to the classification of parts of speech and terminology can be observed in the work Chinese Grammar by another scholar, Xing Fuyi (邢福义, 1996). Unlike previous grammars, the author divides words not into independent words (实词) and auxiliary words (虚词), but into component words (成分词) and non-component words (非成分词), that is, words that can function independently as sentence elements and words that cannot perform such a function. From this definition and grouping, it can be understood that the linguist takes the syntactic properties of words as the principal criterion in their classification.

The first group includes:

Nouns	(名	词)
Verbs	(动	词)
Adjectives	(形	容	词
Adverbs (副词))

The second group includes:

Prepositions	(介	词)
Conjunctions	(连	词)
Auxiliary words (助词))

The scholar classifies words that are associated with a particular function in the sentence, but does not include in either of these two groups words that are not associated with such a function, yet can express meaning independently. He creates a third category, namely the category of special component words (特殊成分), which includes:

Pronouns	(代	词)
Numerals	(数	词)
Measure words	(量	词)
Interjections	(叹	词)
Imitative words (象声词))

Even in this classification, imitative words remain within a separate special group. The main reason for this is that imitative words are similar to independent words in that they can express meaning on their own, but they are also similar to auxiliary words in that they do not answer

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questions in a sentence, cannot function as sentence elements, and are always separated from the sentence by commas. If imitative words are regarded as belonging to one of the two groups, then the definitions that contradict the characteristics of that group would automatically invalidate the classification. Therefore, we consider it more appropriate to leave imitative words within the framework of a separate part of speech.

Wang Li puts forward the following view: “Imitative words arise through imitation of various sounds in the surrounding world; in writing and in language, they do not necessarily have to reproduce the sound exactly. It is sufficient that they indicate a natural sound and that the listener understands it. Such sounds are studied not by grammar, but by stylistics; however, since their expression requires a special linguistic form, they must also be studied grammatically.” He calls imitative words “拟声词” and gives examples such as 哈哈, 咕咕, 咕咚, 哇, and 嘟嘟. In classifying words into parts of speech, the linguist also does not take imitative words into account; he interprets them as a separate rule in Chinese grammar. According to him, imitative words primarily help a person mentally visualize a natural phenomenon. Their function in language is not to reproduce a sound or repeat it exactly, but to distinguish among various sounds and to convey to the listener precisely what is being imitated.

Ma Zhen, in defining onomatopoeic words, states that they express imitation of sounds in nature and gives examples such as 轰轰, 噼噼啪啪, and 叮叮当当. According to the scholar, based on morphological classification, parts of speech in Chinese are divided into two groups: independent words and auxiliary words. However, there are two parts of speech that do not possess a nominative feature, cannot answer questions, and whose function in the sentence is not to connect words to one another. These parts of speech are interjections and imitative words (Table 1.1). Imitative words exist in the lexical stock of every language; they can be translated into different languages, can form sentences independently, and can also function as sentence elements. Taking these factors into account, Mr. Ma recognizes imitative words as the fifteenth part of speech in Chinese within the framework of the special word class.

Table 1.1

No.	实词	虚词	特殊的一类词
1	名词	介词	叹词
2	动词	连词	象声词
3	形容词	助词	
4	状态词	语气词	
5	区别词		
6	数词		
7	量词		

No.	实词	虚词	特殊的一类词
8	代词		
9	副词		

A group of several linguists led by Ding Shengshu (丁声树), on the other hand, divides Chinese words into ten parts of speech and includes imitative words as the final category. However, using the term “sound-like words,” that is, 象声词, they list among 象声词 those words belonging to 感叹词 (gǎntàn cí, interjections), since these reflect various sounds and, without conveying any specific meaning, merely represent sounds produced by human beings: 啊 a, 唉 āi, 喂 wèi, 哼 hēng, 哟 yō, 啦 la, 嗨 hāi.

1. 名词
2. 代词
3. 数词
4. 量词
5. 动词
6. 形容词
7. 副词
8. 连词
9. 助词
10. 象声词

The Chinese linguist Zhu Dexi (朱德熙) defines sounds that express a person’s attitude toward a particular situation and reflect emotions and feelings as words expressing emotional exclamation. The scholar divides Chinese words into 17 parts of speech and forms two large groups from them (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2

Major group	Subgroup	Parts of speech
实词	体词	1. 名词
		2. 处所词
		3. 方位词
		4. 时间词

Major group	Subgroup	Parts of speech
		5. 区别词
		6. 数词
		7. 量词
		8. 代词
	谓词	9. 动词
		10. 形容词
虚词		11. 副词
		12. 连词
		13. 介词
		14. 助词
		15. 语气词
		16. 拟声词
		17. 感叹词

From the standpoint of whether a word can answer a question, Zhu Dexi divides words into two groups: 实词 (independent words) and 虚词 (auxiliary words). He explains his views through an analysis of the functions of words. 实词 are words that can express meaning independently, can function as primary and secondary sentence elements, and denote meanings such as object, action, state, quality, place, and time. 虚词, on the other hand, are primarily words that connect sentence elements or words that form part of a grammatical structure; they are determined by the function of the words to which they are connected and do not express meaning independently. However, words expressing emotional exclamation and words imitating sounds are not included in either of these two groups, but are left separate. Imitative words resemble auxiliary words in that they do not answer questions and lack nominative features, while they are close to independent words in that they can express meaning on their own and perform syntactic functions in the sentence. Perhaps for this reason Zhu Dexi did not include these two categories within the main groups.

Thus, prominent Chinese linguists have been divided into several groups according to their views on assigning imitative words to a particular category. Scholars such as Lü Shuxiang, Zhang Jing, and Liao Xudong advanced the idea of including imitative words within the category of adjectives and attempted to substantiate their views in their works. Lü Shuxiang stated: "The form

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of imitative words is very similar to the form of adjectives; therefore, recognizing them as a subtype of adjectives cannot be considered groundless.” Zhang Jing, in his works *A Comparative Grammar of Ancient and Modern Chinese* and *A New Book of Modern Chinese*, includes imitative words among adjectives under the name 象声形容词 and emphasizes that the grammatical function and form of adjectives and imitative words are identical.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdurahmonov, G'. (2008). *Historical Grammar of the Uzbek Language*. Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan. 530 p.
2. Qo'ng'urov, R. (1996). *Descriptive Words in the Uzbek Language*. Tashkent: Fan. 155 p.
3. Rahmatullayev, Sh. (2006). *Modern Literary Uzbek (textbook)*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 432 p.
4. Usmanov, S. (1952). *Interjections in Modern Uzbek*. Tashkent: Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. 210 p.
5. Karimov, A. (2003). *Measure Words in Chinese: A Lexical-Semantic, Structural and Functional Analysis*. Monograph. Tashkent: Fan va texnologiyalar. 120 p.
6. Mustafayeva, S. (2016). *The Formation and Development of the System of Linguistic Terms in Chinese*. Tashkent: Sharq. 196 p.
7. Ma, Jianzhong. (1987). *Mashi Wentong*. Beijing: Shangwu. 231 p.
8. Zhu, Dexi. (1999). *Collected Works of Zhu Dexi*. Beijing: Shangwu. 397 p.
9. Wang, Li. (2011). *Grammar of Modern Chinese*. Beijing: Shangwu. 427 p.
10. Ding, Shengshu, Lü, Shuxiang, Li, Rong, & Bo, Qing. (1999). *On the Grammar of Modern Chinese*. Beijing: Shangwu. 243 p.
11. Ma, Zhen. (2015). *Practical Chinese Grammar*. Beijing: Beijing Language and Culture University Press. 345 p.
12. Tashmuxamedova, D. A. Q. (2023). XITOY TILIDA TAQLID SO'ZLARNING MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(12), 324-330.
13. Tashmuxamedova, D. A. Q. (2022). DUNYO TILSHUNOSLIGIDA TAQLID SO'ZLAR BORASIDAGI LEKSIK-SEMANTIK QARASHLAR TAHLILI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 21), 65-70.